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VALIDATED RP-HPLC METHOD FOR SIMULTANEOUS DETERMINATION OF IBUPROFEN AND PSEUDOEPHEDRINE IN PHARMACEUTICAL FORMULATION

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ABSTRACT

An accurate, precise and reproducible reverse-phase HPLC method has been developed and validated for the simultaneous estimation of Ibuprofen and Pseudoephedrine in combined dosage form. Separation was achieved using Eclipse Phenyl 3.5 μ , column (150 \times 3.0mm) and Methanol: 0.05% Triethylamine Buffer (4:96) pH adjusted to 7.0 with o-phosphoric acid as mobile phase which shows sharp and resolved peak at a flow rate 0.7 mL/min and UV detection at 210 nm. The linearity of the proposed method was evaluated for the concentration range of 12-240 μ g/mL ($r = 0.9999$) for Ibuprofen, 7.2-145 μ g/mL ($r = 0.9999$) for Pseudoephedrine. The retention time for IBU and PSD were found to be 8.26 and 4.999 respectively. The mean % estimation and recovery of the drugs was found near to 100 % representing the accuracy of the method. Validation of the proposed method was carried out for its accuracy, precision, specificity and ruggedness according to ICH guidelines. The proposed method can be successfully applied in routine work for the determination of Ibuprofen and Pseudoephedrine in combined dosage form.

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INTRODUCTION

Ibuprofen (IBU) is a drug used in the treatment of pain, fever inflammation migranes Rheumatoid Arthritis. IBU, chemically [1] is α -methyl (4-(2-MethylPropyl) Benzeneacetic acid. It is very soluble in alcohol. Pseudoephedrine (PSD) is a stimulant, but it is well known for shrinking swollen nasal mucous membranes, so it is often used as a decongestant. PSD [2] chemically is α -[1-(methylamino) ethyl]-Benzene methanol Hydrochloride. It is sparingly soluble in water and very soluble in ether and alcohol. Literature survey revealed that the methods reported earlier were only for the analysis of single drug and in combination of drugs. Methods are reported for Ibuprofen with Methocarbamol [3], with paracetamol [4], with pseudoephedrine [5] [6] [7] and in ternary mixture [8], quaternary mixture [9] for their determinations in pharmaceutical formulation. The work done earlier on the combination utilises a costlier solvent acetonitrile and the run time of the analysis is also higher, hence our aim was to use less costlier solvent and reduce the run time for the analysis. This paper presents simple, accurate, reproducible, rapid RP-HPLC method for simultaneous analysis of the components in tablet formulation.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Instrumentation and Condition

Shimadzu HPLC chromatograph equipped with pump LC-10 ADvp, SPD-10 M UV detector, Rheodyne Manual injector 7725i with 5 μ L loop and a reversed-phase 3.5 μ Eclipse phenyl column (150 x 3.0 mm) with pore size of 100 $^{\circ}$ A was used for the chromatographic studies and Methanol: Buffer 0.05% Triethylamine Buffer (4:96) pH adjusted to 7.0 as mobile phase which shows sharp and resolved peak at a flow rate 0.7 mL/min and UV detection at 210 nm. HPLC grade water and whatman filter paper (no.41) were used throughout the experimental work.

Materials

Multi-component tablet containing (IBU 200mg and PSD 30mg) was used during the analysis. All chemicals and reagents used were of HPLC grade. All the pure drugs samples supplied by Granules India Ltd., and were used without further purification.

Preparation of stock and standard solution

Mix Stock solution containing IBU and PSD was prepared in diluent (buffer:acetonitrile:80:20) having concentration 120 μ g/mL IBU and 72 μ g/mL PSD.

Preparation of buffer solution

Triethylamine, 5.0mL was dissolved in 960.0mL of waters HPLC grade water and 40.0mL methanol and sonicated. pH was adjusted to 7.0 with orthophosphoric acid.

Development and validation of HPLC Method

Present study was aimed to obtain a new sensitive, cost-effective and convenient method for HPLC determination of ibuprofen and pseudoephedrine in tablet dosage form. The method was validated for the parameters like system suitability, linearity, accuracy, precision, and robustness.

System suitability

The system suitability was assessed by six replicate analysis of mix standard at a 100% level to verify the resolution and reproducibility of the chromatographic system adequate for the analysis to be done. This method was evaluated by analyzing the repeatability of retention time, peak area, tailing factor for IBU and PSD. Also theoretical plates (Tangent) of the column and resolution between the peaks of IBU and PSD were monitored

Specificity (Placebo Interference)

Weighed about Placebo equivalent to 5 tablet preparations into 250mL volumetric flask, added 140mL of diluent and rotary shaking was done for 20 minutes at 200rpm. Then 80mL of diluents was added, sonicated for 20 minutes with intermediate shaking cooled to room temperature and made up the volume with the diluent. The solution was filtered through 0.45 μ m Nylon filter. About 6.0mL of the filtered solution was transferred into 50mL volumetric flask and the volume made up with diluent.

Linearity and Range

Linearity of the method was determined by constructing calibration curves. Standard solutions of IBU and PSD at different concentrations level (10%, -200%) were used for this purpose. Aliquots of mixed standard stock solution were diluted in range 0.6mL to 4.8mL in a series of 50mL for 10% level and 20 mL volumetric flasks with diluent, volumes were made up to mark with diluent to obtain concentration 12-240 μ g/mL for IBU and 7.2-144.0 μ g/mL for PSD. Before injection of the solutions, the column was equilibrated for at least 30min with the mobile phase. The peak areas of the chromatograms were plotted against the concentrations of IBU and PSD to obtain the calibration curves. The eight concentrations of the mix standards were subjected to regression analysis to calculate calibration equation and correlation coefficients.

Assay in Marketed Formulation

Weighed sample equivalent to 5 tablet preparations into 250mL volumetric flask, to it was added 140mL of diluent and rotary shaken for 20 minutes at 200rpm. Then 80mL of diluents was added sonicated for 20 minutes with intermediate shaking, cooled to room temperature and the volume made up with diluent. The sample was centrifuged for 10minutes at 5000RPM and the solution filtered through 0.45 μ m Nylon filter. About 6.0mL of the filtrate was transferred into 50mL volumetric flask and the volume made up with the diluent.

Accuracy

The accuracy is the closeness of agreement between the true value and test result. Accuracy was determined by means of recovery experiments, by addition of active drug to placebo formulations at five levels (50%, 75%, 100%, 125% and 150%). Weighed Pseudoephedrine API, Ibuprofen API and placebo equivalent to 5 tablet preparation into 250mL volumetric flask, to it added 140mL of diluent and rotary shaken for 20 minutes at 200rpm. Then 80mL of diluents was added, sonicated for 45 minutes with intermediate shaking and the volume made up with diluent. The samples were centrifuged for 10minutes at 5000RPM and filtered through 0.45 μ m Nylon filter. About 6.0mL of the filtered solution was transferred into 50mL volumetric flask and the volume made up with diluent. Three replicates at each level selected. The accuracy at each level was calculated from the test results as the percentage of the analyte recovered by the assay.

Precision

The precision of the method was determined by performing six repeated analysis of the sample solutions. The relative standard deviation (% RSD) was determined in order to assess the precision of the method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

HPLC method development and optimization

The optimized chromatographic condition mentioned below was kept constant throughout the experimentation and mobile phase was allowed to equilibrate with stationary phase which was indicated by a steady line.

Column	- Eclipse phenyl 3.5 μ column (150 X 3.0mm)
Detection Wavelength	- 210 nm
Flow rate	- 0.7 mL/min
Temperature: Ambient	- (28-30°C)
pH	- 7.0
Mobile Phase	- METH : Buffer :: 4:96

A 5 μ L solution of above mix standard was injected through manual injector and chromatogram was recorded using mobile phase. IBU and PSD were resolved properly with sharp peak and showing reasonable retention time in the above selected mobile phase. A standard chromatogram for blank and drugs so recorded in shown in fig 1a and 1b respectively.

Fig 1a: Chromatogram for Blank .

Fig 1b: Chromatogram for Mix standard.

Study of system suitability parameters

After equilibration of column with mobile phase, six replicate injections of 5 μ L solution of mix standard solution was injected through the manual injector and the chromatograms were recorded and the system suitability parameter were noted and values are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Observations of System Suitability Parameter.

Parameters	PSD	IBU
Retention time	4.976	8.256
Tailing factor	1.1	1.1
Theoretical Plates	15251	4057
Resolution		

Specificity (Placebo interference)

No Placebo interference with the main peaks of Ibuprofen and pseudoephedrine was observed.

Study of Linearity

The graphs of concentration of drug vs. area under curve were plotted for both the drugs. The correlation coefficient, intercept, slope and Bias calculated are recorded in Table 2.

Table 2: Results of Linearity study.

Parameters	Pseudoephedrine	Ibuprofen
Correlation Coefficient	0.9999	0.9999
Intercept	12699	10234
Slope	14992	12394
Bias	1.2	0.7

Assay

The content of PSD and IBU were calculated by comparison of the standard area with sample area and results are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Results of assay.

S.No	Sample	% Assay Pseudoephedrine	% Assay Ibuprofen
01	Sample-1	100.8	99.1
02	Sample-2	101.2	99.6
03	Sample-3	101.0	98.9
04	Sample-4	101.1	99.1
05	Sample-5	100.8	98.8
06	Sample-6	101.6	99.4
Mean		101.08	99.15
%RSD		0.3	0.3

Accuracy

To ensure the reliability and accuracy of the method recovery studies were carried out by standard addition method. A known quantity of pure drug was added to placebo and contents were analysed by proposed method and the mean % recovery were calculated at each level for IBU and PSD are recorded in Table 3a and 3b respectively.

Table 3a: Results of accuracy for PSD.

Accuracy Level	%Recovery for Pseudoephedrine	% Average of Pseudoephedrine	% RSD
50% Preparation-1	100.8		
50% Preparation-2	100.2	100.5	0.3
50% Preparation-3	100.5		
75% Preparation-1	99.5		
75% Preparation-2	98.9	99.23	0.31
75% Preparation-3	99.3		
100% Preparation-1	100.0		
100% Preparation-2	100.0	99.87	0.23
100% Preparation-3	99.6		
125% Preparation-1	101.1		
125% Preparation-2	100.7	101.0	0.26
125% Preparation-3	101.2		
150% Preparation-1	100.7		
150% Preparation-2	101.0	100.87	0.15
150% Preparation-3	100.9		

Table 3b: Results of accuracy for IBU.

Sample Name	%Recovery for Ibuprofen	% Average of Ibuprofen	% RSD
50% Preparation-1	102.0		
50% Preparation-2	101.6	101.83	0.2
50% Preparation-3	101.9		
75% Preparation-1	100.3		
75% Preparation-2	100.4	100.83	0.83
75% Preparation-3	101.8		
100% Preparation-1	99.3		
100% Preparation-2	100.1	99.9	0.53
100% Preparation-3	100.3		
125% Preparation-1	98.8		
125% Preparation-2	99.1	99.1	0.3
125% Preparation-3	99.4		
150% Preparation-1	100.1		
150% Preparation-2	99.5	99.77	0.31
150% Preparation-3	99.7		

Precision

Precision was evaluated by preparing 6 samples as per test method for Ibuprofen and Pseudoephedrine Tablets and % RSD for both were found to be 0.3 for Ibuprofen and 0.3 for Pseudoephedrine both, was found to be well within the acceptance criteria.

CONCLUSION

Method development of Ibuprofen and Pseudoephedrine with reference to the USP method individual method was modified to form a combined method To obtain a stable baseline by altering the chromatographic conditions and isocratic programme was done. Based on finalized condition during development, % assay of Ibuprofen and Pseudoephedrine was found satisfactory without any interference of blank/placebo with a stable baseline. Hence validation of the test method for the estimation of % assay of Ibuprofen and Pseudoephedrine by HPLC was done. The method can be adopted for routine quality control of the said drugs in combined formulation

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